

Description of *Cantharis navka* sp. n. (Coleoptera: Cantharidae), a third species of the genus from Rovno amber

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ABSTRACT

A new extinct species of a soldier beetle, *Cantharis navka* sp. n. (Cantharidae: Cantharinae), from the late Eocene Rovno amber, is described. This is a third member of the genus registered in Rovno amber, compared to eleven species of *Cantharis* Linnaeus, 1758, known from Baltic amber. The possible use of the length ratio of antennomeres 2 and 3 for separation of the fossil species of *Cantharis* is briefly discussed.

KEYWORDS: Amber, Cantharidae, Cantharinae, Eocene, extinct species, fossil species, new species, paleoentomology, paleontology, Priabonian, Rovno amber, soldier beetle, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The soldier beetle genus *Cantharis* Linnaeus, 1758, belonging to the tribe Cantharini (Cantharinae), is widely distributed in the Holarctic realm, penetrating into the adjacent Neotropic and Oriental Regions, and accounting for over 250 extant species, with the greatest diversity reached in the Western Palaearctic Region (Delkeskamp 1977; Kazantsev & Brancucci 2007).

The amber record of *Cantharis* had until recently been confined to Baltic amber, from where the genus was first reported as *Cantharis* sp. (Helm 1896; Zang 1905; Hieke & Pietrzeniuk 1984), followed by the recent discoveries that brought the number of its members to eleven (Kuška 1992; Kazantsev 2018; Fanti & Pankowski 2020; Pankowski & Fanti 2025). In contrast, the Rovno amber fauna lists just eight Cantharidae species, four in each of Cantharinae and Malthininae (Kazantsev 2010; 2025; Kazantsev & Perkovsky 2014; 2020; Fanti & Pankowski 2023; Kazantsev *et al.* 2024; 2025; Fanti 2025). Two of the Rovno amber cantharines belong to genus *Cantharis* (Fanti & Pankowski 2023; Fanti 2025). Rovno amber is thought to be contemporaneous to Baltic amber yet originated much more southerly (on Volhynian Uplift), compared to the latter (Perkovsky *et al.* 2007, 2010; Mänd *et al.* 2018; Chemyreva *et al.* 2024; Eskov *et al.* 2026). The amber piece with the inclusion was collected supposedly at the Velyki Telkovichi

deposit (Varash District, Rovno Oblast, Ukraine). During the last twelve years Varash District yielded quite a lot inclusions never found in the better studied, nearby located Klesov deposit (reviewed by Fedotova *et al.* 2024; Perkovsky *et al.* 2024), e.g. a tribe of Dryinidae new to science (Olm *et al.* 2022), a moss genus new to science (Ignatov *et al.* 2025), first records of different insect and plant groups for Rovno amber: snakeflies (Perkovsky & Makarkin 2019), tiger beetles (Matalin *et al.* 2021), paussine beetles (Kirichenko-Babko & Perkovsky 2023), ship-timber beetles (Yamamoto *et al.* 2022), sawflies (Vilhelmsen *et al.* 2024). Also, the first *Sphagnum* ever found from Eocene ambers, was found in Velyki Telkovichi (Ignatov *et al.* 2019).

An opportunity to study new amber material from the Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev, has yielded an inclusion with a *Cantharis* specimen that turned out to be a male of a new taxon, a third *Cantharis* species from Rovno amber.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The studied specimen was found in a clear piece of raw amber 41×19×15 mm weighing 7.4 g. Such pieces of amber originated on trunks of amber trees (Perkovsky *et al.* 2012).

The holotype is housed in the Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev (SIZK).

Photographs were taken using a Leica Z16 APO stereomicroscope equipped with a Leica DFC 450 camera.

TAXONOMY

Family Cantharidae Imhoff, 1856 (1815)

Subfamily Cantharinae Imhoff, 1856 (1815)

Tribe Cantharini Imhoff, 1856 (1815)

Genus *Cantharis* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus *Cantharis* Linnaeus, 1758

Cantharis Linnaeus, 1758: 400. Type species: *Cantharis fusca* Linnaeus, 1758: 401, subsequent designation by C.G. Thompson (1859).

Oripa Motschulsky, 1860: 398. Type species: *Oripa transmarina* Motschulsky, 1860: 400, subsequent designation by Delkeskamp (1977).

Silotrachelus Solsky, 1882: 31. Type species: *Silotrachelus semirufus* Solsky, 1882: 33, subsequent designation by Delkeskamp (1977).

Telephorus J.C. Schaeffer, 1766: pl. CXXIII. Type species: *Cantharis fusca* Linnaeus, 1758: 401, subsequent designation by Latreille (1810).

***Cantharis (Cantharis) navka* Kazantsev & Perkovsky, sp. n.**

Figs 1–4

LSID: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:F290EACF-9153-4494-9E8E-435D61FA2557.

Etymology: The name of the new species is a Ukrainian noun ‘navka’, a female forest spirit, who has no back, alluding to the condition of the inclusion in the amber piece.

Diagnosis: *Cantharis navka* sp. n. differs in following characters from the two *Cantharis* spp. from Rovno amber: from *C. groehni* Fanti, 2025 in the greater size (body length almost 1 cm versus 6 mm in *C. groehni*) and uniformly dark brown legs (Figs 1–3) versus apparently bicolored, with testaceous femurs and tibiae and dark tarsi, in *C. groehni*; from *C. michaeli* Fanti & Pankowski, 2023 in the relatively shorter antennomere 3, 1.3× longer than antennomere 2, versus 1.8× longer in *C. michaeli*, and the relative length of antennomeres 2 and 3 combined, ~1.3× longer than that of antennomere 4, versus 1.8× longer in *C. michaeli* (Figs 1, 2, 4). The new species is easily distinguishable from the similar *Cantharis* species from Baltic amber with filiform antennae by the distinctly shorter antennomere 3.

Description: Male. Dark brown to black (Figs 1–3). Body length, 9.6 mm; width (at humeri), ~2.3 mm.

Head transverse, large, densely rugulose. Eyes relatively small, spherical, interocular distance ~1.6× longer than eye diameter in dorsal view. Ultimate maxillary and labial palpomeres wide, noticeably wider than preceding palpomeres; ultimate maxillary palpomere ~2.3× longer than wide, widest at middle; ultimate labial palpomere ~1.5× longer than wide, widest in proximal 2/5. Clypeus convex, medially minutely emarginate. Cheeks short, conspicuously shorter than eye diameter. Antennae filiform, reaching over mid-elytra; scapus (antennomere 1) only slightly wider than antennomeres 2 and 3; antennomere 3 ca. 1.3× as long as antennomere 2; antennomeres 2 and 3 combined ca. 1.3× as long as antennomere 4 and subequal in length to antennomeres 5–11; antennal pubescence short, dense and sub-erect (Figs 1, 2, 4).

Elytra elongate, ~3× longer than wide at humeri, completely covering folded hind wings, with dense decumbent pubescence (Figs 1, 3).

Legs long and slender; femurs and tibiae narrow, subequal in length; tibiae slightly curved, distally with a pair of similar spurs; tarsomeres elongate, in the middle tarsus tarsomere 2 subequal in length to tarsomere 3 and ca. 1.7× shorter than tarsomere 1; outer claw of all tarsi with a distinct rounded apically tooth (Figs 1–3).

Ultimate sternite triangular, about as long as wide; penultimate sternite broadly concave at distal margin (Figs 1, 3).

Female. Unknown.

Holotype: ♂ SIZK VT-497, **Ukraine:** Rivne Region [Rovno Oblast], Varash District, Velyki Telkovichi; Rovno amber, Priabonian, Eocene.

Syninclusions: Numerous detritus pieces, stellate hairs.

Remarks: The layer of amber above the holotype of *Cantharis navka* sp. n. is completely destroyed, therefore no characters related to the upper side are presented in the description. The underside of the specimen, however, offers a reasonably good view of its antennae, legs, abdomen and head, including the palps, their morphology suggesting this is a male specimen of the genus *Cantharis*. Although the

Figs 1–4. *Cantharis (Cantharis) navka* sp. n., holotype male: (1) habitus, ventral view; (2) anterior part, ventral view; (3) posterior part, ventral view; (4) antennomeres 1–4. Scale bars: Fig. 1 = 1 mm, Figs 2–4 = 0.5 mm.

layer of amber above is absent, the outline of the elytra is easily traced, as well as their pubescence at the edges, which is indicated in the description. The line drawing of antennomeres 1–4 (Fig. 4) represents their actual shape and relative length defined by observation, whereas the obscuring properties of the amber piece and the position of the inclusion prevented from taking a photo of the antennae at a right angle.

The elongated second antennomere of the new species is somewhat reminiscent of the genus *Themus* Motschulsky, 1858, in which the antennomere 2 is often longer, or only slightly shorter than antennomere 3. However, its toothed outer claw and the short cheeks suggest it does not belong in *Themus*, but in *Cantharis* (Medvedev & Ryvkin 1992; Švihla 1992; Kazantsev 2001, 2013).

DISCUSSION

Some of the *Cantharis* species known from Baltic amber have been described from females only (Fanti & Pankowski 2020; Pankowski 2023; Pankowski & Fanti 2025), regrettably also both Rovno amber species, *C. groehni* and *C. michaeli*, are known from females only (Fanti & Pankowski 2023; Fanti 2025), whereas the modern systematics is based on the distinguishing characters of males, while female characters are not widely used to separate species, especially closely related ones (e.g., Brancucci 1980; Švihla 1992, 1999; Kazantsev 2022). Hence, there arises a question, if it would be possible to compare already described species known only by females — with presumably new ones represented by males.

The structure of claws appears to be of little help, as the extant *Cantharis* species usually have, to a greater or lesser extent, a different claw structure in males and females (Švihla 1992; Kazantsev 2022). On the other hand, the analysis of the relative lengths of male antennomeres 2 and 3 shows that the antennomere 2 is always considerably shorter than the antennomere 3 in the extant European *Cantharis* species (Kuška 1995; Kazantsev 2022). Although the antennae and antennomeres tend to be shorter in females, the length ratio of antennomeres 2 and 3 remains roughly the same in both sexes. Therefore, it seems appropriate to use the difference in relative antennomere lengths, when it is considerable, as is in the case with *Cantharis navka* sp. n., to distinguish between males and females of different species. The new species appears to have characters of both *Cantharis* (the toothed male outer claw and short cheeks) and *Themus* (the insignificant length difference of antennomeres 2 and 3).

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